

Correlation between Parental Styles and Emotional Intelligence on Juvenile Delinquency among Secondary School Students in Kaduna-South, Local Government Area, Kaduna State

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Abstract

The study investigated the correlation between parental styles and emotional intelligence as predictors of juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna State. A correlational research design was adopted. The population of two thousand nine hundred and nineteen (2,919) students were obtained, the sample size of 333 senior secondary students (SSS II) at a confidence level of 95% and a Margin Error of 5.0%. Ten schools were selected using stratified sampling techniques based on gender and simple randomly sampling techniques to select respondents. The instrument used consists of three sections namely an adapted Parenting Styles Questionnaires (PSQ), Students' Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire (SEIQ) Section "C" contained Students' Juvenile Delinquency Questionnaire (SJDQ) with reliability coefficient of 0.745, 0.853 and 0.702, respectively. Five hypotheses were formulated and tested using multiple regression, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient and t-test at 0.05 level of significance. Result analysis of the study showed the relative importance of each of the predictor variables (parenting styles and emotional intelligent) to the prediction of juvenile delinquency with $R=0.136$. This indication $R^2 = 0.716$ is a good level of prediction, which is equivalent to 51.6%, indicating the level of shared variance between the dependent variable and the independent variables ($F_{c=331, 1.525} < 0.05$). Based on these findings, it was recommended among others that: Parents, guardians and caregivers should appreciate the need to create a peaceful home with relative harmony in development of pro-social behaviour on the part of the children.

Keyword: Parenting Styles, Emotional Intelligent, Juvenile Delinquency, Secondary School Students

Introduction

The contemporary landscape of adolescent behaviour is marked by an increasing prevalence of juvenile delinquency, which poses significant challenges to the well-being of societies worldwide. Among the myriad of factors contributing to this issue, the role of parenting styles and emotional intelligence has gained substantial attention in recent psychological research. Parenting styles is characterized by various combinations of parental responsiveness and demandingness, have been linked to a range of behavioral outcomes in adolescents. Parenting style is a process of care, nurturing, guiding and educating from parents to their children (Muhammad & Norhida, 2020). Parenting style is an important aspect that influences the well-being of children, creating a functional family and illuminates the image of the parent outside the word. According to Maccorby and Martin (1983); Baumrind (2003) practice and behaviour that are implemented to educate children will have a direct effect towards emotion, social and intellect of the child. They used these two domains to identify four styles of parenting: Democratic, Autocratic, Permissive, and Neglectful. Each domain fits to the four parenting styles and includes the proportion of each parenting style used by mothers and fathers in the current study.

Democratic parents are the role models for overall effective child socialization and adaptive behavioural outcomes because democratic parents offer the right balance of warmth and support, while creating a constructive and flexible disciplinary arrangement (Mike, Leanne & Country, 2018; Laurson, & Collins, 2009). These parents are open to bidirectional communication and teach their children self-control (Trinkner, Cocha, Rebellion & Van Gundy, 2012). This mix of positive parental attributes was congruent with low levels of problem behaviours in children (Mike et al, 2018). Democratic parenting refers to authoritative parents, authoritative provided the strongest buffer against delinquency, but

even one authoritative parent provided some protection (Simons & Conger, 2007). Democratic parenting style is found to suit the children's needs the best. These parenting styles has a high responsive level but low demand as parents put more focus on care, autonomy and negotiate rules with the child (Igbo & Ihejiene, 2014; Nik & Mohd 2018). Meanwhile, democratic parenting style has a low responsive level yet high demand because it concerned with the compliance towards parents, practiced control approach, punishment and rigid rules.

Autocratic parents elicit rigid discipline, little to no flexibility, and a highly structured environment. These parents tend to be highly controlling with less receptivity to their children's preferences (Mike et al., 2018). Overtly strict parenting may inhibit their children's personal growth and independence. As children resist the controls on freedom, they become more likely to rebel by turning to delinquency. Autocratic styles also known as authoritarian parenting styles were moderately likely to lead to negative outcomes for youths (Trinkner et al., 2012). Muhammad and Norhida, (2020) authoritarian parenting style affects children's behaviour as they have to obey the parents' instructions without being given the freedom to make their own decision. This causes the children to feel constrained and did not get enough control over activities that they love. Later on, it could result to lower confidence among children in exploring new opportunities, inability to adapt themselves to a challenging social network and feeling bored with their life (Rika & Sri, 2017).

Permissive parents tend to be highly supportive, approachable, and lenient. However, permissive parents do not establish boundaries for their children and rarely enforced the rules. As a result, society may see permissive parents as less legitimate (Trinkner et al., 2012). Students who perceived their fathers as permissive had less socially desirable adjustment outcomes than youths who perceived their fathers as authoritarian or authoritative (Mike et al, 2018). It is noted that failure to monitor and control their children's behaviour, and to recognize and punish deviant behaviour, leads to lack of self-control in children, further increasing the risk of delinquency (Hoeve et al., 2008). Muhammad and Norhida (2020) opined that permissive parenting style leads their children to engage in social misconducts such as drugs abuse, property crimes and vandalism.

Additionally, another variable in this study is emotional intelligence which encompassing the ability to perceive, understand, and manage emotions effectively, is recognized as a crucial determinant of adaptive behavior and psychological well-being. Emotional intelligence was introduced by John Mayer and Peter Salovey in early 1990, in their attempt to develop a scientific measure for knowing the difference in peoples' ability in the areas of emotions. Emotional intelligence is the ability to monitor one's own and other people's emotions, to discriminate between different emotions and label them appropriately, and to use emotional information to guide thinking and behaviour (Bada, Jimoh & Ibrahim, 2022; Colman, 2003). Emotional intelligence may be defined as the capacity to reason with emotion in four areas: to perceive emotion, to integrate it in thought, to understand it and to manage it.

Emotional Intelligence provides a fresh angle on investigating human feelings; it's not surprising that it has caught the attention of scholars and scientists (Raham, Gurantulain, Talha, Syed & Ayesh, 2022). Emotionally intelligent people are resilient enough to push through difficult feelings to reach their goals (Owan, 2022). Sensitivity and control over various emotional experiences (Adeleke, 2008). According to Meher, Rajashree and Sadhujan (2021) Emotional Intelligence is the capacity or ability of an individual for perceiving, processing, knowing and regulating emotional information accurately in an effective manner involving Intra and inters abilities to guide one's thinking to make certain changes in others. Emotional intelligence is the ability to perceive, manage and regulate emotions, promoting adaptive thinking and the understanding of the meaning and consequences of emotions.

In the context of education, Juvenile behaviour refers to failure of a student in obeying rules that are set and committing in actions that do not abide the law. A student can be categorized as delinquent when they act in a contradicting, misleading and negative manner to break the rules and crime laws (Rozmi et al., 2017). This behavioural misconduct contradicts the societal norms and cannot be accepted as they are still students. The antisocial behaviours often associated with the juvenile delinquents include vandalism, drug abuse, weapon carrying, alcohol abuse, rape, examination malpractices, school violence, bullying, cultism, truancy, school drop-outs, to mention but a few (Kudirat, et al., 2010). It is problematic behaviours portray the image of bad action, damaged morality and negligence of being responsible, which also deciphered as actions that violate the ethics in religion and life norms that bring harms to soul and damage good values in one self (Ahmad, Ummi, Mustafa & Mohammed 2019). Obviously, unless something is done to roll back the wave of juvenile delinquency, the prospect of a better, safer and more prosperous society emerging in Nigeria will remain elusive. Understanding the interplay between parenting styles, emotional intelligence, and juvenile delinquency is essential for developing targeted intervention programs and support mechanisms for adolescents. Therefore, exploring these relationships among senior secondary school students in a specific context, such as Kaduna state, becomes imperative for tailoring interventions to the unique socio-cultural and environmental factors in that region.

Social learning theory paved the way for the development of a new theory – social disorganization theory. Social disorganization theory was introduced by Shaw and McKay (1969). This theory proposed that crime and delinquency could be attributed to the rapid growth, urbanization, immigration, and breakdown in community supports in addition to the replacement of traditional values with criminal values. The application of social structural theories

requires researchers to look beyond the individual when attempting to make sense of criminal behaviour among youths (Sumithra & Komalavalli, 2022). This theory helped to explain the higher crime rates, both juvenile and adult (Hartinger Saunders & Rine, 2011). When applying social disorganization theory to possible prevention techniques and diversionary programs, it is important to understand that the underlying foundation of this theory is community responsibility.

Despite the significance of parenting styles and emotional intelligence in shaping adolescent behavior, there is a notable gap in the existing literature concerning their collective impact on juvenile delinquency, particularly among senior secondary school students in Kaduna state. The problem at hand lies in the insufficient understanding of how specific parenting styles, ranging from democratic and permissive to autocratic, might influence the development of emotional intelligence in adolescents and subsequently contribute to or protect against engagement in delinquent behaviors. This knowledge gap hinders the formulation of targeted preventive strategies and interventions tailored to the unique cultural and contextual factors of Kaduna state. According to Ajokpaniovo, Awoyemi, Okesina and Anyanwu (2021), delinquency is a disturbing issue confronting students, parents and teachers alike. Taking together the increase in the number and severity of such acts and their overwhelming cost for the society validates the notion that delinquency has become a prominent national issue. In all its ramifications, juvenile delinquency has destructive and dysfunctional effects on the lives of individuals involved. The antisocial behaviours associated with juvenile delinquents include drug abuse, alcohol abuse, examination malpractices, school violence, bullying, cultism, truancy, school drop-outs etc (Kudirat, et al., 2010).

Moreover, the rising rates of juvenile delinquency in Kaduna state underscore the urgency of investigating these factors to inform evidence-based policies and interventions. This study seeks to address this gap by examining the nuanced relationships between parental styles, emotional intelligence, and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students, aiming to provide valuable insights for educators, parents, and policymakers in Kaduna state and beyond. It is against this backdrop that, this study will investigate the correlation between parental styles and emotional intelligence as predictors of juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state

Objectives of the Study

The objective of this study is to investigate the correlation between parental styles and emotional intelligence as predictors of juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state. Specifically, the study intends:

1. To investigate the combined influence of parental styles, emotional intelligence and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state
2. To find out the relationship between democratic parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state
3. To examine the relationship between autocratic parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state
4. To examine the relationship between permissive parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state
5. To find out the relationship between emotional intelligence and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state

Research Question

The following research question was used to guide the study.

1. What is the level of parental styles among secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area of Kaduna State?

Hypothesis

The following hypotheses were formulated for the study:

1. Ho₁: There is no significant combined influence of parental styles, emotional intelligence and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state
2. Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between democratic parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state

Ho₃: There is no significant relationship between autocratic parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state

Ho₄: There is no significant relationship between permissive parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state

Ho₅: There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state

Methodology

The research design of correlational type of descriptive study was employed by the researcher to carry out the research work. The correlational design was preferred to determine if there is a relationship between or among the variables (parental styles, emotional intelligence and juvenile delinquency). The population for the study was comprise of all public senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state. The population for this study are senior secondary school (SSS II) students which comprises of two thousand, nine hundred and nineteen (2,919) students as per 2023/2024 academic session. A total sample size that is appropriate for the research was three hundred and thirty-three (333) students were sample size for the study, which comprises of 170 male and 163 female students (respondents). The sample size estimation is in line with recommendations offered at a confidence level 95% and a Margin Error of 5.0% (Research Advisor, 2006).

Stratified sampling technique was adopted to select sample for the study because it involves grouping large population into definite characteristics. The researcher grouped the schools into two based on gender i.e. single schools. The researcher selected ten (10) schools from the Kaduna South local government area through simple randomly sampling techniques in the local government area. The purposive sampling techniques was used to select sample schools based on co-education and gender four (4) co-education, three (3) Girls' only and three (3) Boys' only for the study. This sample was appropriate when the researcher selects subjects that are considered, were in a better position to provide the required information sought for and each subject have equal chance to be selected for the study. The senior secondary school (SSS II) students were selected because they are in semi-final stage/exit-class of secondary school.

The instrument for this study is questionnaires, which was divided into sections 'A', 'B' and 'C'. Section "A" elicit information on demographic data of the respondents such as; Name of school, age, and gender. The Section 'B' instrument titled Parental styles Questionnaire (PSQ), was adapted from Erinisha (2012). It is sub-divided into three scales: Democratic Parenting Style Scale, Autocratic Parenting Style Scale and Permissive Parenting Style Scale. The Section 'C' instrument which was titled Students' Emotional Intelligence Questionnaires (SEIQ), developed and adapted version of Goleman (1998), items are mostly suitable students to investigate their intelligence. Ten (10) items were selected for the purpose of the study, which have strong link with individual emotions. The Section 'D' instrument which was titled Students' Juvenile Delinquency Questionnaire (SJDQ) was self-designed from reviewed literature. The items were drawn from literature for its relevance to the subject matter, appropriateness of the text content and coverage of the content area. This consists of 10 items which measured students' juvenile delinquency. All consist of four (4) points likert moderated scale.

The instrument was subjected to validation, the face and content validity of the instrument by two experts from educational psychology and Counselling Department, Federal University Dutsin-ma, Katsina State. The point of validation will be to assess the structuring of the instrument, to verify the adequacy of the instrument as well as to weight the responses expected from the respondents. The test-retest method of reliability was used in pilot testing of instrument to determine the reliability of the instruments. The instrument was administered to a sample of twenty (20) students from, which is not part of the real study sample. Test re-test reliability method was used to carry out with an interval of three weeks between the first and second administration of the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was obtained after the pilot testing; using Cronbach Alpha Statistical analysis. The following Alpha coefficient values of the following were obtained on the following instruments Parental styles Questionnaire (PSQ) has 0.745, Emotional Intelligence Questionnaires (EIQ) has 0.853, and Students' Juvenile Delinquency Questionnaire (SJDQ) has 0.702. Frequency and simple percentage, mean was used to analyze the data collected. Multiple regressions analysis was used to test hypothesis 1, Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistics was used to test hypotheses 2, 3, 4 and 5. All hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Data collected was subjected to SPSS Version 23 statistical software.

Presentation of Results

Research Question: Which parental styles is the common used by parents as perceived by senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area of Kaduna State?

Table 1: parental styles mostly used by parents as perceived by senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area of Kaduna State

S/N	Parental Styles	Mean	Aggregate Mean Ranking order
1.	Democratic parenting styles	15.58	3 rd
2.	Autocratic parental styles	15.79	2 nd
3.	Permissive parental styles	15.84	1 st
Weighted Mean Score		15.74	3.15

Table 1 revealed that democratic parenting style had a mean of 15.58 (3.12), while autocratic parental styles had a mean of 15.79 (3.16) and permissive parental styles 15.84 (3.17) respectively. It shows that all the three parental styles were above the acceptance aggregate mean point of 3.00. This implied that the three parental styles were mostly contributed to juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state, which the acceptance aggregate mean score.

Testing of Hypothesis

Ho₁: There is no significant combined influence of parental styles, emotional intelligence and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state.

Table 2: Regression Analysis combined influence of parental styles, emotional intelligence and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard Error
1	0.136 ^a	0.716	0.018	2.83540

Analysis of Variance					
Model	Sum of Square	Df	Mean Square	F	S
Regression	49.050	4	12.262	1.525	.004 ^b
Residual	2620.884	329	8.040		
Total	2669.934	331			

a. Dependent Variable: SJDQ

b. Predictors: (Constant), DPS, APS PPS SEIQ,

The analysis on table 2 shows that parental styles and emotional intelligence accounted for 71.6% of -the total variance in student's English achievement ($R^2 = 0.716$, p -value = 0.004, $p < 0.05$). This percentage is statistically significant. Therefore, parental styles and emotional intelligence have significant combined influence on juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state. The results reveal that parental styles and emotional intelligence are important factors that significantly influence juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between democratic parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state

Table 3: Correlation between democratic parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students

Variable	N	Mean	S.D	DF	Cal. r-value	Sig.(2-tailed)	Decison
Democratic parental styles	333	15.58	2.14	331	0.237*	0.034	Rejected
Juvenile Delinquency	333	20.64	2.84				

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The result on table 3 shows that there are significant relationship between democratic parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state ($r = .237$, p -value = 0.034), since $p < 0.05$ level of significant, therefore, hypotheses two was rejected. Hence, the democratic parental styles have great influence juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students.

Ho₃: There is no significant relationship between autocratic parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state

Table 4: Correlation between autocratic parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students

Variable	N	Mean	S.D	DF	Cal. r-value	Sig.(2-tailed)	Decison
Autocratic parental styles	333	15.79	2.34	331	0.123*	0.025	Rejected
Juvenile Delinquency	333	20.64	2.84				

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

The result on table 4 shows that there are significant relationship between autocratic parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state ($r = .123$, p -

value = 0.025), since $p < 0.05$ level of significant, therefore, hypotheses two was rejected. Hence, the autocratic parental styles have great influence juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students.

Ho4: There is no significant relationship between permissive parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state

Table 5: Correlation between permissive parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students

Variable	N	Mean	S.D	DF	Cal. r-value	Sig.(2-tailed)	Decison
Permissive parental styles	333	15.84	2.20	331	0.049*	0.374	Accepted
Juvenile Delinquency	333	20.64	2.84				

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

The result on table 5 shows that there are significant relationship between permissive parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state ($r = .237$, p -value = 0.034), since $p > 0.05$ level of significant, therefore, hypotheses two was accepted. Hence, the permissive parental styles have great influence juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students.

Ho5: There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state

Table 6: Correlation between Emotional Intelligence and juvenile delinquency among Senior Secondary School Students

Variable	N	Mean	S.D	DF	Cal. r-value	Sig.(2-tailed)	Decison
Emotional Intelligence	333	15.86	2.20	331	0.126*	0.022	Rejected
Juvenile Delinquency	333	20.64	2.84				

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

The result on table 6 shows that there are significant relationship between emotional intelligence and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state ($r = .126$, p -value = 0.022), since $p < 0.05$ level of significant, therefore, hypotheses two was rejected. Hence, the emotional intelligence has great influence juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students.

Discussion of Findings

Research question revealed that democratic parenting style had a mean score of 15.58 (3.12), while autocratic parental styles had a mean score of 15.79 (3.16) had a mean score of and permissive parental styles 15.84 (3.17) respectively. This implied that all the three parental styles were mostly contributed to juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state. The finding of this study corroborates with Mowen, (2011) results indicate that shifts from autocratic parenting style correlate with increase in juvenile delinquency. Correspondingly, a shift from autocratic parenting to democratic parenting is shown to correlate with increase in juvenile delinquency. A shift from permissive to authoritative parenting also corresponded with an increase in juvenile delinquency between waves as each style has contribute traits to juvenile delinquency.

The result of hypothesis one revealed that significant combined influence of parental styles and emotional intelligence have significant combined influence on juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state. This implies that parental styles and emotional intelligence have significant combined influence on juvenile delinquency. The finding of this study corroborates with Rubina and Martin (2016) found that autocratic parenting style was associated with lower levels of juvenile delinquency, whereas permissive parenting was associated higher levels of delinquency. Moreover, democratic parental styles showed lower relationships with juvenile delinquency than autocratic parental styles. In addition, Sumithra and Komalavalli (2022) revealed that emotional intelligence significantly predicts drug abuse among students, truancy etc. The findings however mean that an individual's level of self understanding and others can actually determine if she will be involved in drug use and abuse. It means that for students to be involved in drug abuse like alcoholism, smoking and others, their level of perception of self and other will come into play from this. Rex (2011) suggests that as emotional intelligent increases delinquency decreases. The study also looked at how emotional intelligent influences the decision-making process of juveniles and increases their chance of engaging in deviant, delinquent, or criminal behaviour.

The result of hypothesis two revealed that there is significant influence of democratic parental styles on juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state. This implies that parental styles and emotional intelligence have a great influence on juvenile delinquency on students. The finding of this study corroborates with Kudirat et al (2010) claimed that family cohesiveness of democratic parental styles significantly influences juvenile delinquency among secondary school student Thus it is clear that family stability has a significant influence on juvenile delinquency among secondary school students. Muhammad and Norhida (2020) found that there is a significant relation between democratic parenting style and juvenile delinquent behaviour.

The result of hypothesis three revealed that there is significant influence of autocratic parental styles on juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state. This implies that autocratic parental styles have a great influence on juvenile delinquency on students. The finding of this study corroborates with Muhammad and Norhida (2020) see that autocratic parental styles show significant relationship. This means that parents control and restrict the freedom of their children influence the behaviour of juvenile students. Rubina and Martin (2016) findings show that autocratic style is a parenting style that contributes towards the control the juvenile delinquent among students. This study comes in line with the research where they found that autocratic parenting style tends to instill negativity among children as they received education that is too constrained and forceful.

The result of hypothesis four revealed that significant influence permissive parental styles on juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state. This implies that permissive parental styles have a great influence on juvenile delinquency on students. The finding of this study corroborates with Muhammad and Norhida (2020) found that permissive parental styles do not show any significant relationship. This means that parents who like to control and restrict the freedom of their children influence the behaviour of juvenile students. Permissive parenting style was associated with the highest level of youth delinquency in the analysis. This finding was consistent with previous research that compared the parental styles (Simons & Conger, 2007).

The result of hypothesis five revealed that significant emotional intelligence on juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state. This implies that emotional intelligence have a great influence on juvenile delinquency on students. The finding of this study corroborate with Narke and Gangurde (2022) found a positive association found between emotional intelligence of juvenile delinquency. Noreen and Carmelita (2022) shows that juveniles sometimes manifested the level of emotional intelligence Moreover, it was also proved that high school students possessing deficiencies in the level of emotional intelligence show greater predictability toward violent and criminal tendencies

Conclusion

The juvenile delinquents, parental styles and emotional intelligence are elusive but valuable concepts. It can assess a person's social fit and make improvements. From the findings, it is evident that both parental styles and emotional intelligence of juvenile delinquents should be guided and developed so as to reduce the crimes performed by them at a young age. The juvenile delinquent is a serious social problem that necessitates action, and if the strength of the link between emotional intelligence and can be determined, effective interventions can be put in place. Proper parental styles, empathy and self-control tools can be taught to troubled youth to help them become productive members of society. It's a fascinating study area with a great deal of application in our current society, especially concerning juvenile delinquents and emotional intelligence.

Recommendations

1. Parents, guardians and caregivers should appreciate the need to create a peaceful home with relative harmony in development of pro-social behaviour on the part of the children.
2. Teachers as well parents should try to ensure that students report to school as at when due, measures to minimize the level of delinquency should be put in place.
3. Educational psychologist and school counsellor should intensify their effort to organize seminar on implication of juvenile delinquency.
4. Students should be guide and encouraged against any form of juvenile delinquency that can affect their academic pursuit and developed their emotions and creativity in vocational training tailored to their skills and interests.

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